

**THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF THE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT ON
THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ADAPTIVE REASONING AND
MATHEMATICAL ENGAGEMENT AMONG
FIRST-YEAR STUDENTS**

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The Mediating Effect of the Learning Environment on the Relationship Between Adaptive Reasoning and Mathematical Engagement among First-Year Students

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the learning environment's mediating effect on the relationship between adaptive reasoning and mathematical engagement among first-year students. The study was quantitative, non-experimental research that utilized descriptive-correlational and mediation analyses. Using stratified random sampling, specifically proportional allocation for the sampling techniques, and Slovin's formula with a 0.05 margin of error for the sample size, 258 randomly selected students across all programs were the respondents. Results showed high levels of adaptive reasoning, mathematical engagement, and learning environment. Results also revealed significant relationships between adaptive reasoning and mathematical engagement, between adaptive reasoning and learning environment, and between learning environment and mathematical engagement. Moreover, the results showed that the learning environment partially mediated the relationship between adaptive reasoning and mathematical engagement.

Keywords: *adaptive reasoning, mathematical engagement, learning environment, Philippines*

Introduction

The problem of lack of engagement among students is a prevalent concern encountered by numerous educators. Numerous scholarly investigations have examined the phenomenon of student participation within the educational setting. Promoting effective participation in mathematics remains a persistent and ongoing challenge (Bennett & Boesdorfer, 2020). Collie et al.'s (2019) research supports this argument, indicating a decline in student engagement with and motivation to persist in mathematics as they advance through compulsory education. Furthermore, it has been observed that kids who exhibit high levels of engagement demonstrate regular attendance at school and have superior academic performance compared to their peers who display low levels of engagement (Bear et al., 2018).

In the global setting, a significant proportion of students, ranging from 40% to 60%, in urban, suburban, and rural areas are experiencing disengagement. This issue has increased in various nations, such as the United States, Australia, Finland, and France (Collie et al., 2019). Moreover, the correlation between mathematics achievement and engagement is significant, and the decline in engagement poses a potential risk to students' performance and achievement in secondary mathematics courses (Schuetz et al., 2018).

In the Philippines, difficulties have been encountered in mathematics education, and it obtained the lowest ranking in international assessments (San Juan, 2019). According to the PISA 2018 International Report, the average score in mathematical literacy for students from the Philippines was 353 points, notably lower than the average score of 489 points seen among students from the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). This discrepancy suggests that Filipino pupils demonstrated a skill level below Level 1, as defined by the OECD (2019). According to the 2019 Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) conducted by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement, the Philippines achieved a score of 297 in mathematics (Mullis et al., 2019).

With that, conducting a study about the mediating effect of the learning environment on the relationship between adaptive reasoning and mathematical engagement displayed by college students in mathematics requires in-depth research. The discipline of mathematics frequently evokes feelings of intimidation and detachment among several students, resulting in lower involvement and poor academic achievement. Obtaining insight into the impact of the learning environment on students' attitudes and motivation toward mathematics might assist educators in developing enhanced pedagogical approaches.

Moreover, the present study added another body of literature, as no existing studies used the variables in the present study within one single study. Hence, the present study will fill the gap by generating a new body of literature. To cite an established study, the research conducted by McMinn et al. (2020), titled "Learning Environment, Self-Efficacy for Teaching Mathematics, and Beliefs About Mathematics," stated that a positive learning environment and high self-efficacy for teaching mathematics are associated with more positive beliefs about mathematics. In addition, the study conducted by Susilawati et al. (2021), titled "Adaptive Reasoning Based on Microsoft Mathematics," found that the implementation of search learning significantly enhanced students' adaptive reasoning abilities. Lastly, Ayub et al. (2017) conducted a study titled "Disparities in Mathematics Engagement Among Students Based on Gender and School Location." The results found that gender differences were not significant, but there were noteworthy variations in mathematics engagement based on the school location. However, these studies did not delve into the mediation analysis of the learning environment on adaptive reasoning and mathematical engagement. Thus, this study is motivated by the recognition of this gap. I aim to address it by investigating the mediating role of the learning environment in the relationship between adaptive reasoning and mathematical engagement among first-year students.

Lastly, this research will be widely shared with the public through print and digital formats. Academic conferences and publications will be used to reach future researchers, while instructional materials and engaging presentations will target students. Collaboration with institutions and participation in relevant forums will ensure awareness and involvement. This approach aims to make this research accessible and applicable to diverse audiences.

Research Questions

This study aims to examine the mediating effect of the learning environment on the relationship between adaptive reasoning and mathematical engagement. To be specific, this study seeks to answer to the following objectives:

1. To determine the level of adaptive reasoning of first-year students in terms of:
 - 1.1. proposition of a correct conjecture;
 - 1.2. drawing the correct conclusion;
 - 1.3. finding the correct pattern of a problem;
 - 1.4. presentation of correct reasoning, and
 - 1.5. examination of an argument.
2. To determine the level of mathematical engagement of first-year students in terms of:
 - 2.1. cognitive engagement;
 - 2.2. affective engagement; and
 - 2.3. behavioral engagement.
3. To determine the level of the learning environment of first-year students in terms of:
 - 3.1. motivation to exert learning effort;
 - 3.2. activate towards self-regulated learning;
 - 3.3. feedback and coach; and
 - 3.4. structure and steer.
4. To determine the significant relationship between:
 - 4.1. adaptive reasoning and mathematical engagement;
 - 4.2. learning environment and mathematical engagement; and
 - 4.3. adaptive reasoning and learning environment.
5. To determine the mediating effect of the learning environment on the relationship between adaptive reasoning and mathematical engagement.

Methodology

Research Design

This investigation employed a quantitative, non-experimental research approach, explicitly utilizing a correlational technique and mediation analysis. In this context, mediating variables refer to behavioral, biological, psychological, or social constructs that serve as conduits for the influence of one variable on another. Mediation analysis allows researchers to elucidate the processes or mechanisms through which one variable impacts another. Non-experimental research, as defined, is characterized by the absence of manipulating an independent variable and the lack of random assignment of individuals to conditions or the ordering of conditions. It is important to note that grouping these methods solely based on what they lack might be somewhat unjust (Price et al., 2014).

In this research, non-experimental approaches allow the investigator to observe and comprehend the inherent associations between adaptive reasoning, the learning environment, and mathematical engagement among first-year students. By scrutinizing these relationships without intervening in variables, the study aims to provide significant insights into the impact of individual differences and learning preferences on mathematical performance. These findings can provide valuable information for shaping educational strategies and developing curricula within teacher education programs.

Moreover, descriptive studies play a pivotal role in the research design by furnishing methodologies for summarizing, examining, and understanding data. They provide valuable perspectives on the central tendencies, variability, and data distribution. Statistical measures such as mean, median, and mode depict average values, while metrics like range, variance, and standard deviation illuminate the extent of data dispersion. Visualization tools like histograms, box plots, and frequency tables provide a clearer understanding of data distribution. These tools are instrumental in making informed decisions based on data, recognizing patterns, and conveying research findings effectively (Price et al., 2014).

In this research, descriptive study, specifically descriptive statistics, enables the researcher to summarize, analyze, and comprehend the collected data succinctly. This approach facilitates gaining valuable insights into the central tendencies related to adaptive reasoning, the learning environment, and mathematics engagement within our participant group. Descriptive statistics play a crucial role in quantifying the variability of these variables and presenting their distribution visually, thereby simplifying the identification of patterns and trends. Furthermore, these statistical methods serve as the fundamental framework for developing a more profound understanding of the intricate interplay among these variables. Ultimately, this aids in drawing meaningful conclusions from our research findings.

Correlational research is a non-experimental investigation where the researcher examines the statistical relationship between two variables without actively controlling external factors. This approach focuses on analyzing the correlation between variables rather than implementing strict experimental controls. Researchers opt for correlational studies over experiments for two primary reasons, as Price et al. (2014) outlined.

In this context, employing a correlational approach proves beneficial. Correlational research enables researchers to explore the statistical connections between variables, such as adaptive reasoning, learning environment, and mathematics engagement, without actively manipulating these elements in a controlled setting. This methodology proves advantageous for the study as it recognizes the intricate nature of real-world educational environments. This comprehension is vital for customizing impactful teaching strategies and fostering students' achievements in mathematics, even when working within the limitations of a non-experimental approach.

In its simplest version, mediation analysis includes a third variable to this $X \rightarrow Y$ relation. The third variable, M , is linked between X and Y , whereby X causes the mediator, M , and causes Y , so $X + M \rightarrow Y$. (MacKinnon et al., 2007).

The independent variable here in this study is adaptive reasoning, while the dependent variable is mathematics engagement, and the mediating variable is a learning environment. In this study, the researcher determined the relationship between adaptive reasoning and mathematics engagement and the mediating effect of the learning environment on the relationship between adaptive reasoning and mathematics engagement of all first-year students across all programs.

Respondents

The respondents for this research consisted of first-year students across all programs at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology (KCAST) during the first semester of the 2023–2024 academic year. The selection of these participants is based on the research's emphasis on examining the correlation between adaptive reasoning and mathematics engagement within the learning environment context. Focusing on first-year students at KCAST is considered appropriate and justified due to the primary emphasis on mathematics engagement. This study used the stratified random sampling method to ensure a randomized and scientifically robust sampling strategy. This method divides the population into subgroups or strata based on specific, relevant characteristics such as age, gender, or academic performance. Subsequently, a random sample is chosen from each of these strata. The rationale for opting for stratified random sampling is to maintain randomness in participant selection and uphold the scientific integrity of the study. This method guarantees that the selected sample accurately represents the broader population and that each subgroup is adequately and proportionally included. The objective is to enhance the generalizability of the study's findings. It is essential to note that successfully implementing stratified random sampling requires a well-defined population and a clear understanding of the relevant characteristics for stratification (Etikan & Bala, 2017).

Stratified random sampling was employed in this study because it aligns well with the research context. The participants were first-year students across all programs at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology (KCAST). They were chosen through a random sampling method with strata defined based on their academic majors. The researcher formally requested population data from the college registrar to establish the sample size. Subsequently, the obtained data was handed over to a statistician, who conducted the necessary calculations to determine the sample size for the study.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Bachelor of Elementary Education (Generalist)	187	14	0.41%
Bachelor Of Public Administration	440	33	0.96%
Bachelor of Science in Agriculture (Animal Science)	134	10	0.29%
Bachelor of Science in Agriculture (Horticulture)	231	17	0.50%
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (Financial Management)	317	24	0.69%
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (Human Resource Management)	121	9	0.26%
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (Marketing Management)	396	30	0.86%
Bachelor of Science in Criminology	692	52	1.51%
Bachelor of Science in Office Administration	393	29	0.85%
Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English	223	17	0.49%
Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Filipino	191	14	0.42%
Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Mathematics	119	9	0.26%
Total	3444	258	7.49%

Instrument

The study adopted three downloadable questionnaires from web sources to measure the variables. The instruments for learning environments are from the study conducted by Vandecandelaere et al. (2012), and the instruments for mathematics engagement are from the study conducted by Camabaya et al. (2022). The learning environment questionnaire scale has a 5-point Likert type. The learning environment was measured with five items on the scale. The scores that can be obtained from the scale range from 1 to 20. A

high score indicates a higher learning environment. While the mathematics engagement questionnaire scale has a 5-point Likert type with a Cronbach Alpha of 0.90. The scores that can be obtained from the scale range from 1 to 15.

Moreover, the instrument for adaptive reasoning is from the study *The use of creative problem-solving models to develop students' adaptive reasoning abilities: inductive, deductive, and intuitive* by Ansari et al. (2020). The adaptive reasoning questionnaire has five factors: the proposition of a correct conjecture, drawing the correct conclusion, finding the correct pattern of a problem, presenting correct reasoning, and examining an argument. The five items in each subscale showed adequate internal consistency reliabilities, with Cronbach's alpha coefficients above the cut-off points of 0.90. The following five-point Likert-type scale was used to describe the adaptive reasoning questionnaire.

For the questionnaires, as mentioned earlier, the researcher used the Likert scale, a method of assigning quantitative values to make data amenable to statistical analysis. The researcher assigned a numerical value to each potential choice and computed a mean figure for all the responses at the end of the evaluation or survey. The final average score represents the overall level of perceptions as manifested (Term, 2004).

Procedure

In collecting, the researcher took the following steps:

Questionnaire Development. The researcher searched the questionnaires from journal articles related to the three variables.

Revision and Validation of Questionnaires: After formulating the questionnaire, it was used and submitted to a panel of experts for evaluation and contextualization. The researcher will follow the advice of these revision experts until it is approved for use.

Requesting Approval to Carry out the Study. The researcher asked permission to conduct this from the Vice President of Academic Affairs at the research locale through a formal letter. This letter should be signed by the researcher and noted by his research adviser and the Director of Research and Development.

Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. Survey questionnaires in printed forms were distributed individually to the respondents, who are first-year students roaming around the campus.

Collection and Tabulation of the Data. After the survey, the researcher took and analyzed the research instrument to record the collected data from the respondents. The statistical data was analyzed, and the findings will subsequently be interpreted. Based on the final data set, conclusions were drawn, and the learning assessment results formulated recommendations.

Data Analysis

The data gathered through the questionnaires was tallied and treated using the following statistical tools. The following statistical tools were used in the computation of data and to test the hypotheses at a significance level of 0.05.

Mean. The average of a set of values is a statistical measure calculated by adding up all the values in a data set and then dividing that sum by the total number of data points. It is a fundamental tool used to assess various characteristics, such as adaptive reasoning, mathematics engagement, and learning environment, by providing a representative value that summarizes the central tendency of the data.

Pearson-r Correlation. This was used to determine the relationship between adaptive reasoning and mathematical engagement, learning environment and mathematical engagement, and adaptive reasoning and learning environment, which are the variables of this study.

Mediation Analysis. This was carried out to determine whether the mediating variable impacts the relationship between an independent and dependent variable using the indirect effect. This research was utilized to determine whether the learning environment mediates the relationship between adaptive reasoning and mathematics engagement by addressing the main statement of the problem.

Ethical Considerations

The participants of this study were first-year students from all programs of the Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology. To ensure the sound conduct of the study, ethical considerations were addressed and considered accordingly.

Informed Consent. The term consists of two essential components: informed and consent, which necessitate meticulous study. Participants must possess comprehensive knowledge of the tasks they expected to perform, how the data was utilized, and the potential ramifications, if any. Participants are required to provide explicit, active, and signed consent to participate in the study. This consent includes acknowledging their rights to access their data and the option to withdraw from the study at any point. Informed consent is a formal agreement between the researcher and the participants (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

In this case, the researcher includes an informed consent question in a printed survey form, asking the study's respondents if they are still willing to participate despite the risks. When the respondents are unsure about the agreement, they may choose to decline. Making informed decisions and participating in the study voluntarily are strongly encouraged. The researcher ensures that all the respondents in the study are enthusiastic about it and eager to participate. It is critical to base their responses on the available surveys while gathering

data.

During the informed consent process, the respondents are oriented toward the following rights that they have: The respondents are informed that they have the right to terminate participation without any need for explanation. They also have the right to refuse to answer sensitive questions. Another right they have is the entitlement to ask questions about the study. Lastly, they also have the right to be informed of the study results after this research is accomplished.

Risk of Harm, Anonymity and Confidentiality. The respondent's information must be consistently safeguarded and treated with utmost confidentiality, extending beyond mere anonymity by refraining from disclosing their identity or related details. Ensuring anonymity and secrecy are crucial to protecting individuals from potential damage (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

There is a possible risk of harm in terms of social liabilities when the data is carefully disclosed to others. The study data shall be kept private and secured to avoid this incident. The researcher emphasized to the respondents that their safety, identity, and personal information would be protected and that their participation in the study would be necessary. To create an error-free collection, the researcher removes identities from the data. A clean data collection does not contain any data that could be used to identify the respondents, such as names or addresses (such identifying data could be stored in separate, secure files elsewhere). Data shall be stored and destroyed three years after the study is accomplished.

Conflict of Interest. The researcher's current affiliations or past activities may lead to a conflict of interest, which must be openly declared in an ethics approval application. This allows the committee to offer guidance on managing the conflict (Blanco, 2023). Nevertheless, the study's researcher affirms that the research was conducted independently, without any affiliations or financial connections that may be seen as a conflict of interest.

This perspective asserts that external variables did not influence the research outcomes since the participants were also students, and the researcher had no conflicting interests with the study. Conflict of interest occurs when a researcher possesses the authority to employ coercive tactics, such as threats of termination of benefits, blackmail, or other forms of punishment, to compel respondents to participate. For instance, this may involve principals threatening to dismiss teachers or teachers threatening to fail their students if they refuse to respond to the survey.

Results and Discussion

Level of Adaptive Reasoning of Students in Terms of Proposition of the Correct Conjecture

The level of adaptive reasoning was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, proposition of the correct conjecture. The responses of first-year students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 2 is the level of adaptive reasoning of students in terms of the proposition of the correct conjecture. The data revealed that the level of adaptive reasoning in terms of the proposition of the correct conjecture had a total mean of 3.91 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of adaptive reasoning of students in terms of the proposition of the correct conjecture is oftentimes manifested.

Table 2. *Level of Adaptive Reasoning of Students in Terms of Proposition of the Correct Conjecture*

Proposition of the Correct Conjecture	Mean	Description
1. Having confidence in my ability to create logical conjecture when faced with mathematically formulated problems.	4.01	High
2. Being comfortable sharing my thoughts and conjectures during collaborative math discussions.	3.85	High
3. Being skilled at distinguishing between valid and invalid conjectures in open-ended discussions.	3.79	High
4. Seeking feedback to improve the accuracy of my conjectures in solving mathematical sequences.	4.03	High
5. Taking pleasure in the process of formulating conjectures for solving algebraic expressions.	3.85	High
OVERALL	3.91	High

The highest mean is 4.03, which is high. This is from Item No. 4 – Seeking feedback to improve the accuracy of my conjectures in solving mathematical sequences. This means that the involved respondents oftentimes manifest the item. However, the lowest mean is 3.79, with a descriptive equivalent of high. This is from Item No. 3 - Being skilled at distinguishing between valid and invalid conjectures in an open-ended discussion. This means that the respondents of the study oftentimes manifest the item.

Level of Adaptive Reasoning of Students in Terms of Drawing the Correct Conclusion

The level of adaptive reasoning was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, drawing the correct conclusion. The responses of first-year students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 3 is the level of adaptive reasoning of students in terms of drawing the correct conclusion. The data revealed that the level of adaptive reasoning for drawing the correct conclusion had a total mean of 3.84 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of adaptive reasoning of students in terms of drawing the correct conclusion is oftentimes manifested.

Table 3. *Level of Adaptive Reasoning of Students in Terms of Drawing the Correct Conclusion*

Drawing the Correct Conclusion	Mean	Description
1. Drawing precise conclusions and deductions from the information presented in math lessons.	3.84	High
2. Being adept at utilizing implicit or inferred details to draw conclusions while engaging with mathematical solutions.	3.78	High
3. Being confident in my proficiency in drawing sound conclusions from various math assignments.	3.83	High
4. Synthesizing information and recognizing patterns enabled me to draw meaningful conclusions.	3.81	High
5. Taking feedback and suggestions is enhancing my ability to draw correct conclusions in my mathematical performance.	3.92	High
OVERALL	3.83	High

The highest mean is 3.92, which is high. This is from Item No. 5 – Taking feedback and suggestions are enhancing my ability to draw correct conclusions in my mathematical performance. This means that the involved respondents oftentimes manifest the item. Similarly, the lowest mean is 3.78, but it has a descriptive equivalent of high. This is from Item No. 2 - Being adept at utilizing implicit or inferred details to draw conclusions while engaging with mathematical solutions. This means that the respondents of the study oftentimes manifest the item.

Level of Adaptive Reasoning of Students in Terms of Finding the Correct Pattern of a Problem

The level of adaptive reasoning was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, finding the correct pattern of a problem. The responses of first-year students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 4 is the level of adaptive reasoning of students in terms of finding the correct pattern of a problem. The data revealed that the level of adaptive reasoning in finding the correct problem pattern had a total mean of 3.87 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of adaptive reasoning of students in terms of finding the correct pattern of a problem is they oftentimes manifested.

Table 4. *Level of Adaptive Reasoning of Students in Terms of Finding the Correct Pattern of a Problem*

Finding the Correct Pattern of a problem	Mean	Description
1. Having confidence in my ability to discern patterns within data when tackling mathematical challenges.	3.90	High
2. Possessing the skill to identify the relevant pattern that can help address my difficulties with mathematical problems.	3.87	High
3. Seeing opportunities for growth in my ability to recognize patterns in mathematical problems.	3.92	High
4. Possessing a strong sense of confidence in my ability to successfully discern the correct pattern when solving mathematical problems.	3.85	High
5. Deriving enjoyment from the active examination and identification of patterns, viewing it as an integral strategy in solving mathematical problems.	3.81	High
OVERALL	3.87	High

The highest mean is 3.92, which is high. This is from Item No. 3 – Seeing opportunities for growth in my ability to recognize patterns in mathematical problems. This means that the respondents of the study oftentimes manifest the item. However, the lowest mean is 3.81, but it has a descriptive equivalent of high. This is from Item No. 5 - Deriving enjoyment from the active examination and identification of patterns, viewing it as an integral strategy in solving mathematical problems. This means that the respondents of the study oftentimes manifest the item.

Level of Adaptive Reasoning Students in Terms of Presentation of Correct Reasoning

The level of adaptive reasoning was measured through the survey questionnaire, which indicated correct reasoning. The responses of first-year students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 5 is the level of adaptive reasoning of students in terms of the presentation of correct reasoning. The data revealed that the level of adaptive reasoning in terms of the presentation of correct reasoning had a total mean of 3.90, with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of adaptive reasoning of students in terms of the presentation of correct reasoning is oftentimes manifested.

Table 5. *Level of Adaptive Reasoning of Students in Terms of Presentation of Correct Reasoning*

Presentation of Correct Reasoning	Mean	Description
1. Expressing my thoughts and concepts in a well-organized manner.	4.17	High
2. Being good at organizing my math presentations so that ideas flow smoothly from one to the next.	3.83	High
3. Being good at presenting and integrating relevant evidence within the realm of mathematics.	3.83	High
4. Presenting accurate reasoning in collaborative math discussions.	3.84	High
5. Considering myself adept at presenting accurate reasoning in the mathematics class.	3.84	High
OVERALL	3.90	High

The highest mean is 4.17, which is high. This is from Item No. 1 - Expressing my thoughts and concepts in a well-organized manner. This means that the involved respondents oftentimes manifest the item.

Similarly, the lowest mean is 3.83, but it has a descriptive equivalent of high. This is from Items No. 2 & 3 - Being good at organizing my math presentations so that ideas flow smoothly from one to the next, & Being good at presenting and integrating relevant evidence within the realm of mathematics. This means that the respondents of the study oftentimes manifest the item.

Level of Adaptive Reasoning of Students in Terms of Examination of an Argument

The level of adaptive reasoning was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, which examines an argument. The responses of first-year students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 6 is the level of adaptive reasoning of students in terms of examination of an argument. The data revealed that the level of adaptive reasoning in terms of examination of an argument had a mean of 3.93 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of adaptive reasoning of students in terms of examination of an argument is oftentimes manifested.

Table 6. *Level of Adaptive Reasoning of Students in Terms of Examination of an Argument*

Examination of an Argument	Mean	Description
1. Feeling proficient in my ability to effectively evaluate arguments in math class.	3.95	High
2. Approaching mathematical arguments with an open mind, considering diverse perspectives on math-related topics.	3.95	High
3. Applying the knowledge acquired in my studies to critically analyze and critique mathematical arguments.	3.97	High
4. Having a strong sense of confidence in my ability to thoroughly examine and assess mathematical arguments.	3.90	High
5. Pinpointing the underlying assumptions embedded in mathematical arguments.	3.87	High
OVERALL	3.93	High

The highest mean is 3.97, which is high. This is from Item No. 3 - Applying the knowledge acquired in my studies to critically analyze and critique mathematical arguments. This means that the involved respondents oftentimes manifest the items.

Furthermore, the lowest mean is 3.87, but it has a descriptive equivalent of high. This is from Item No. 5 - Pinpoint the underlying assumptions embedded in mathematical arguments. This means that the respondents of the study oftentimes manifest the item.

Summary on the Level of Adaptive Reasoning

Presented in Table 7 is the overall level of adaptive reasoning in terms of the proposition of the correct conjecture, drawing the correct conclusion, finding the correct pattern of a problem, presentation of correct reasoning, and examination of an argument. The data revealed that students' adaptive reasoning level has a total mean of 3.89 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that students' level of adaptive reasoning is oftentimes manifested.

Moreover, the highest mean is 3.93, the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of adaptive reasoning as perceived by students in terms of examination of an argument is oftentimes manifested.

Table 7. *Summary on the Level of Adaptive Reasoning*

Adaptive Reasoning	Mean	Description
Proposition of the Correct Conjecture	3.91	High
Drawing the Correct Conclusion	3.84	High
Finding the Correct Pattern of a Problem	3.87	High
Presentation of Correct Reasoning	3.90	High
Examination of an Argument	3.93	High
OVERALL	3.89	High

In contrast, the lowest indicator is drawing the correct conclusion, which obtained a mean of 3.84 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of adaptive reasoning in terms of drawing the correct conclusion is oftentimes manifested.

Moreover, finding the correct pattern of a problem obtained a mean of 3.87, which is high. This indicates that the level of adaptive reasoning in terms of finding the correct pattern of a problem is oftentimes manifested.

Additionally, the proposition of the correct conjecture obtained a mean of 3.91, which is high. This indicates that the level of teaching adaptive reasoning in terms of the proposition of the correct conjecture is oftentimes manifested.

Lastly, the presentation of correct reasoning obtained a mean of 3.90, which is high. This indicates that the level of adaptive reasoning in terms of the presentation of correct reasoning is oftentimes manifested.

Level of Mathematical Engagement of Students in Terms of Cognitive Engagement

The level of mathematical engagement was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator of cognitive engagement. The responses of first-year students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 8 is the level of mathematical engagement of students in terms of cognitive engagement. The data revealed that the level of mathematical engagement in terms of cognitive engagement has a total mean of 4.20 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of mathematical engagement of students in terms of cognitive engagement is oftentimes manifested.

Table 8. *Level of Mathematical Engagement of Students in Terms of Cognitive Engagement*

Cognitive Engagement	Mean	Description
1. Trying to connect what I am learning to things I have learned before.	4.34	Very High
2. Trying to understand my mistakes when I get something wrong.	4.26	Very High
3. Going through the work for math class and making sure that it is right.	4.07	High
4. Thinking about different ways to solve a problem.	4.14	High
5. Being guided to the correct answer rather than having to do work on my own.	4.18	High
OVERALL	4.20	High

The highest mean is 4.34, which is very high. This is from Item No. 1 – Trying to connect what I am learning to things I have learned before. This means that the item is always manifested by the involved respondents.

In contrast, the lowest mean is 4.07 but with a descriptive equivalent of high. This is from Item No. 3 – Going through the work for math class and making sure that it is right. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents of the study.

Level of Mathematical Engagement of Students in Terms of Affective Engagement

The level of mathematical engagement was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator of affective engagement. The responses of first-year students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 9 is the level of mathematical engagement of students in terms of affective engagement. The data revealed that the level of mathematical engagement in terms of affective engagement has a total mean of 4.01 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that students' mathematical engagement level in terms of affective engagement is sometimes manifested.

The highest mean is 4.09, which is high. This is from Items No. 2 & 4 – Wanting to understand what is learned in math class and getting excited when I learn new things about math. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the involved respondents. In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.88 but with a descriptive equivalent of high. This is from Item No. 5 – Feel good when I am in math class. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents of the study.

Table 9. *Level of Mathematical Engagement of Students in Terms of Affective Engagement*

	Affective Engagement	Mean	Description
1.	Enjoying learning about math.	3.94	High
2.	Wanting to understand what is learned in math class.	4.09	High
3.	Enjoying learning new things about math.	4.05	High
4.	Getting excited when I learn new things about math.	4.09	High
5.	Feeling good when I am in math class.	3.88	High
OVERALL		4.01	High

Level of Mathematical Engagement of Students in Terms of Behavioral Engagement

The level of mathematical engagement was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator of behavioral engagement. The responses of first-year students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 10 is the level of mathematical engagement of students in terms of behavioral engagement. The data revealed that the level of mathematical engagement in terms of behavioral engagement has a total mean of 4.02 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of mathematical engagement of students in terms of behavioral engagement is oftentimes manifested. The highest mean is 4.27, which is very high. This is from Item No. 1 –

Keeping trying even something is hard. This means that the item is always manifested by the involved respondents. In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.77, but it has a descriptive equivalent of high. This is from Item No. 4 – Talking about math outside of class. This means that the item is always manifested by the respondents.

Table 10. *Level of Mathematical Engagement of First-year Students Across All Programs in Terms of Behavioral Engagement*

	Behavioral Engagement	Mean	Description
1.	Keeping trying even something is hard.	4.27	Very High
2.	Completing my homework on time.	3.99	High
3.	Exploring diverse interests and opportunities while maintaining focus during designated learning times.	4.06	High
4.	Talking about math outside of class.	3.77	High
5.	Putting effort into learning math.	4.00	High
OVERALL		4.02	High

Summary of the Level of Mathematical Engagement

Presented in Table 11 is the overall level of mathematical engagement in terms of cognitive, affective, and behavioral engagement. The data revealed that students' mathematical engagement level has a total mean of 4.07 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of mathematical engagement of students is oftentimes manifested.

Table 11. *Summary of the Level of Mathematical Engagement*

Mathematical Engagement	Mean	Description
Cognitive Engagement	4.20	High
Affective Engagement	4.01	High
Behavioral Engagement	4.02	High
OVERALL	4.07	High

The highest mean is 4.20, which is the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of mathematical engagement of students in terms of cognitive engagement is oftentimes manifested. In contrast, the lowest indicator is affective engagement, which obtained a mean of 4.01 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of mathematical engagement of students in terms of affective engagement is oftentimes manifested. Lastly, behavioral engagement obtained a mean of 4.02, which is high. This indicates that the level of mathematical engagement of students in terms of behavioral engagement is oftentimes manifested.

Level of Learning Environment of Students in Terms of Motivation to Exert Learning Effort

The level of the learning environment was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator of motivation to exert learning effort. The responses of first-year students across all programs on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 12. *Level of Learning Environment of First-Year Students Across All Programs in Terms of Motivation to Exert Learning Effort*

Motivation to Exert Learning Effort	Mean	Description
1. Having noticed that my teacher makes sure that we get interested in the subject matter.	4.31	Very High
2. Appreciating that my teacher uses an agreeable diversity of approaches in his or her teaching.	4.30	Very High
3. Feeling motivated as we work in a pleasant manner.	4.26	Very High
4. Feeling that my subject matter will be useful to me later.	4.23	Very High
5. Focusing better on a conducive learning environment.	4.09	High
OVERALL	4.24	Very High

Presented in Table 12 is the level of the learning environment of students in terms of motivation to exert learning effort. The data revealed that the level of the learning environment in terms of motivation to exert learning effort had a total mean of 4.24 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicated that the level of students' learning environment in terms of motivation to exert learning effort is always manifested.

The highest mean is 4.31, which is very high. This is from Item No. 1 - Having noticed that my teacher makes sure that we get interested in the subject matter. This means that the item is always observed by the involved respondents. This suggests that students consistently feel engaged and motivated by the teacher's efforts, which is essential to fostering a positive and effective learning environment.

Consequently, the lowest mean is 4.09, but with a descriptive equivalent of high. This is from Item No. 5 - Focusing better on a conducive learning environment. This means that the respondents of the study oftentimes observe the item. This indicates that while students often recognize and experience a conducive learning environment, there may still be areas for enhancement, and further improvements could be made to maximize focus and learning.

Level of Learning Environment of Students in Terms of Activate Towards Self- regulated Learning

The level of learning environment was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator activate towards self-regulated learning. The responses of first-year students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 13 is the level of, learning environment of students in terms of activate towards self-regulated learning. The data revealed that the level of learning environment in terms of activate towards self-regulated learning had a total mean of 4.22 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicated that the level of learning environment in terms of activate towards self-regulated learning is always observed.

The highest mean is 4.32, which is very high. This is from Item No. 4 – Seeing how our teacher gives small clues that help us find solutions by ourselves. This means that the item is always observed by the involved respondents. For instance, the lowest mean is 4.14 but with a descriptive equivalent of high. This is from Item No. 2 - Preferring that my teacher keeps in mind the students' remarks when searching for suitable assignments or practice materials. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents of the study.

Table 13. *Level of Learning Environment of Students in Terms of Activate Towards Self- regulated Learning*

Activate Towards Self-regulated Learning	Mean	Description
1. Finding it beneficial that my teacher gives tasks that encourage us to keep looking for a solution.	4.36	Very High
2. Preferring that my teacher keeps in mind the students' remarks when searching for suitable assignments or practice materials.	4.14	High
3. Appreciating how each new chapter starts with examples from daily life that clarify the new subject.	4.20	Very High
4. Seeing how our teacher gives small clues that help us find solutions by ourselves.	4.32	Very High
5. Being like how situations are described that can happen in the real world and that need a mathematical solution.	4.15	High
OVERALL	4.22	Very High

Level of Learning Environment of Students in Terms of Feedback and Coach

The level of learning Environment was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, feedback and coach. The responses of first-year students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 14 is the level of, learning environment of students in terms of feedback and coach. The data revealed that the level of the learning environment in terms of feedback and coach had a total mean of 4.22 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicated that the level of learning environment in terms of feedback and coach is always manifested.

The highest mean is 4.38, which is very high. This is from Item No. 2 - Appreciating when my teacher repeats the subject matter when it is not properly understood by some students. This means that the item is always observed by the involved respondents.

The lowest mean is 4.05 but with a descriptive equivalent of high. This is from Item No. 1 - Feeling okay when my teacher takes into account students' answers. This means that the respondents of the study oftentimes observe the item.

Table 14. *Level of Learning Environment of Students in Terms of Feedback and Coach*

	Feedback and Coach	Mean	Description
1.	Feeling okay when my teacher takes into account students' answers.	4.05	High
2.	Appreciating when my teacher repeats the subject matter when it is not properly understood by some students.	4.38	Very High
3.	Learning from mistakes when my teacher clarifies errors in tests thoroughly.	4.28	Very High
4.	Feeling guided in lessons when our teacher explains the solution after an exercise.	4.30	Very High
5.	Being encouraged by thinking about what caused the problem and what I can do if an assignment or test goes wrong.	4.10	High
OVERALL		4.22	Very High

Level of Learning Environment of Students in Terms of Structure and Steer

The level of learning environment was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, structure and steer. The responses of first-year students across all programs on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 15 is the level of learning environment as of students in terms of structure and steer. The data revealed that the level of the learning environment in terms of structure and steer had a total mean of 4.30 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicated that students' level of learning environment in terms of structure and steer is always manifested.

The highest mean is 4.40, which is very high. This is from Item No. 4 – Appreciating when the teacher tries to help us understand new subject matter by alternating questions to the class with explanations. This means that the item is always manifested by the involved respondents.

Ultimately, the lowest mean is 4.08, but with a descriptive equivalent of high. This is from item no. 3 - Having the opportunity to explain my solutions to our teacher. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents of the study, showing that students feel supported in expressing their ideas inside the class.

Table 15. *Level of Learning Environment of Students in Terms of Structure and Steer*

	Structure and Steer	Mean	Description
1.	Being thankful for our teacher's approach and that we understand the subject matter well.	4.39	Very High
2.	Supporting the idea that my teacher is able to explain new topics in a clear and organized manner.	4.32	Very High
3.	Having the opportunity to explain my solutions to our teacher.	4.08	High
4.	Appreciating when the teacher tries to help us understand new subject matter by alternating questions to the class with explanations.	4.40	Very High
5.	Appreciating that my teacher keeps the class under control effectively.	4.30	Very High
OVERALL		4.30	Very High

Summary of the Level of Learning Environment

Presented in Table 16 is the overall level of learning environment in terms of motivation to exert learning effort, activate towards self-regulated learning, feedback and coach, and structure and steer. The data revealed that students' learning environment level has a total mean of 4.25 with the descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicates that the level of learning environment of first-year students is always manifested.

As a result, the highest mean is 4.30, which is the descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicates that students' level of learning environment in terms of structure and steer is always observed.

To illustrate, the lowest indicator are activate towards self-regulated learning and feedback and coach which obtained a mean of 4.22 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicates that the level of learning environment of students in terms of activate towards self-regulated learning and feedback and coach is always manifested.

Lastly, motivation to exert learning effort obtained a mean of 4.24, which is very high. This indicates that the level of learning environment of students in terms of motivation to exert learning effort is always manifested.

Table 16. *Summary of the Level of Learning Environment*

Learning Environment	Mean	Description
Motivation to Exert Learning Effort	4.24	High
Activate Towards Self-regulated learning	4.22	High
Feedback and Coach	4.22	High
Structure and Steer	4.30	Very High
OVERALL	4.25	Very High

Significant Relationship Between Adaptive Reasoning and Mathematical Engagement

Presented in Table 17 is the result of the significant relationship between adaptive reasoning and mathematical engagement, $r(256) = .758, p < .001$. Since the probability value ($p < .001$) is less than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), the null hypothesis is rejected. This means a positive and significant relationship exists between adaptive reasoning and mathematical engagement.

Table 17. *Significant Relationship Between Adaptive Reasoning and Mathematical Engagement*

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @ $\alpha=0.05$
Adaptive Reasoning	3.89			
Mathematical Engagement	4.07	.758	<.001	H₀ Rejected

Significant Relationship Between Adaptive Reasoning and Learning Environment

Presented in Table 18 is the result of the significant relationship between multiple intelligence and learning styles, $r(256) = .586, p < .001$. Since the probability value ($p < .001$) is less than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), the null hypothesis is rejected. This means a significant relationship exists between adaptive reasoning and the learning environment.

Table 18. *Significant Relationship Between Adaptive Reasoning and Learning Environment*

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @ $\alpha=0.05$
Adaptive Reasoning	3.89			
Learning Environment	4.24	.586	<.001	H₀ Rejected

Significant Relationship Between Learning Environment and Mathematical Engagement

Presented in Table 19 is the result of the significant relationship between learning environment and mathematical engagement, $r(256) = .683, p < .001$. Since the probability value ($p < .001$) is less than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), the null hypothesis is rejected. This means a positive and significant relationship exists between the learning environment and mathematical engagement.

Table 19. *Significant Relationship Between Learning environment and Mathematical engagement*

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @ $\alpha=0.05$
Learning Engagement	4.25			
Mathematical engagement	4.07	.683	<.001	H₀ Rejected

Mediating Role of Learning Environment on The Relationship Between Adaptive Reasoning and Mathematical Engagement Among First Year Students Across All Programs

Preacher and Hayes's mediation analysis approach was utilized in this study to determine if the learning environment mediates the relationship between adaptive reasoning and mathematical engagement among first-year students across all programs. It is a regression-based bootstrap approach similar to SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) used for analyzing mediation. It consists of two steps that reflect the recommendation for mediation analysis. In step 1, the direct and indirect effects are tested for significance. Step 2 involves

defining the type of effect and mediation, which is classified into partial and complete mediation.

Complete mediation is achieved if the direct effect is not significant and the indirect effect is significant. This means that only the indirect effect of the mediator exists. On the other hand, partial mediation happens when the direct effect is significant.

Mediation Analysis

Table 20 shows the direct effect of adaptive reasoning on mathematical engagement. Based on the result, the direct effect of adaptive reasoning (IV) on mathematical engagement (DV) is significant [$\beta=.522$, $SE=0.043$, 95% CI (0.438,0.607)]. Since the confidence interval in the direct effect does not include zero, it indicates that the direct effect of adaptive reasoning is significant. It also revealed that adaptive reasoning significantly influenced mathematical engagement ($\beta=.523$, $p<.001$). Based on the result, adaptive reasoning significantly influences mathematical engagement even without the learning environment.

Table 20. *Direct Effects*

	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper
IV → DV	0.522	0.043	12.177	0.001	0.438	0.607

Table 21 shows the indirect effect of adaptive reasoning (IV) on the learning environment (MV) and mathematical engagement (DV) showed [$\beta=.204$, $SE=0.031$, 95% CI (0.144, 0.264)], and it indicates that the confidence interval does not include zero. At 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected, $p=0.001$. This announces that the mediating variable, the learning environment, mediates the relationship between the independent variable, adaptive reasoning, and the dependent variable, mathematical engagement.

Table 21. *Indirect Effects*

	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper
IV → MV → DV	0.204	0.031	6.659	0.001	0.144	0.264

Moreover, Table 22 shows that adaptive reasoning significantly influences to mathematical engagement among first-year students across all programs. This means that even without the presence of the mediating variable, the learning environment and adaptive reasoning already affect mathematical engagement among first-year students across all programs. Since the direct effect is significant, it can be concluded that the relationship between adaptive reasoning and mathematical engagement is only partly mediated by the learning environment.

Table 22. *Total Effects*

	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper
IV → DV	0.727	0.039	18.650	<.001	0.650	0.803

Furthermore, Table 23 revealed that adaptive reasoning significantly influenced mathematical engagement, $\beta=.522$, $p=.001$. Also, adaptive reasoning significantly affected the learning environment, $\beta=.498$, $p<0.01$. Lastly, the learning environment significantly predicts mathematical engagement, $\beta=.410$, $p=.001$.

Table 23. *Path Coefficients*

	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper
MV → DV	0.410	0.050	8.129	<0.001	0.311	0.509
IV → DV	0.522	0.043	12.177	<0.001	0.438	0.607
IV → MV	0.498	0.043	11.612	<0.001	0.414	0.582

In addition to the result of the study, Figure 3 shows the path estimates between Adaptive Reasoning and Mathematical Engagement (Path C), Adaptive Reasoning and Learning Environment (Path A), and Learning Environment and Mathematical Engagement (Path B). It revealed that adaptive reasoning significantly influenced mathematical engagement, $\beta=.522$, $p<.001$. Also, adaptive reasoning significantly affected the learning environment, $\beta=.498$, $p<.001$. Lastly, the learning environment significantly predicts mathematical engagement, $\beta=.410$, $p<.001$. These results suggested that the indirect pathway partially mediated the relationship between adaptive reasoning and mathematics engagement through the learning environment. This claim was also supported in Table 21 by the estimation of a significant indirect effect.

Further, the result implies that mathematical engagement should not only be bounded and limited to the adaptive reasoning of students. Teachers should look into other factors affecting a student's mathematics engagement and not just their adaptive reasoning. Perhaps teachers should also consider students' engagement, specifically students' motivation to exert learning effort, activate towards self-regulated learning, feedback and coach, and structure and steer as it partially mediated or significantly affects the relationship of adaptive reasoning and mathematics engagement.

Level of Adaptive Reasoning

The data revealed that the level of adaptive reasoning among students is high. It shows that adaptive reasoning prioritizes developing students' capacity for logical thought and coming up with various alternative solutions to mathematical problem scenarios. This could lead students to enhance their problem-solving abilities and a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts.

This is further supported by Yanti et al. (2020), which states that proficiency in adaptive reasoning empowers students to interact with mathematical concepts more deeply, enabling them to generate diverse alternative solutions in response to mathematical problem scenarios. In this context, higher-order thinking ability supports students in thinking critically, creatively, and reflectively because this thinking skill is a process that requires students to use critical thinking skills to apply previously learned knowledge, which is very important to support increasingly complex problem-solving.

Similarly, this is also supported by the study conducted by Dewi et al. (2020), which explored the relationship between adaptive reasoning skills and procedural fluency among students. The data revealed that they demonstrate logical thinking in selecting appropriate concepts and situations, indicating that students can apply their reasoning abilities effectively when navigating various concepts and scenarios. The findings also highlight the importance of fostering these skills in educational settings, emphasizing their crucial role in shaping students' academic progress.

In addition, another supported study conducted by Rustana and Sumantri (2019) examined the fact that mastery of adaptive reasoning is closely associated with improved scientific literacy. This investigation has shown that adaptive reasoning can influence conceptual comprehension and scientific literacy, highlighting a substantial link, indicating that adaptive reasoning is a key factor in shaping conceptual understanding and scientific literacy.

Furthermore, the study reveals that the level of adaptive reasoning in the proposition of the correct conjecture is high. This revealed that the level of adaptive reasoning of first-year students across all programs in terms of the proposition of the correct conjecture is oftentimes observed. This indicates that the proposition of the correct conjecture serves as a starting point for further exploration and analysis of specific problems, which is essential in helping students generate appropriate ideas for solving logical problems.

This is in congruence with the statement of Weisstein (2019), which stated that the conjectures serve as starting points for further exploration and analysis, encouraging researchers to investigate and either validate or refute the proposed statements through empirical evidence or logical reasoning. In this context, it highlights the crucial role of conjecture in advancing knowledge by inspiring further inquiry and investigation.

Additionally, another supported study conducted by Ellis et al. (2019), which examined the use of examples in exploring conjectures and developing appropriate justifications, distinguished two different ways to view examples connected to different mathematical reasoning processes. However, it revealed that while students could find multiple examples to support the conjecture, they struggled to find counterexamples to refute it. In this context, although students may adeptly generate examples to affirm a conjecture, their ability to identify counterexamples remains crucial to mathematical reasoning development.

The study by Joseph (2021) corroborates this observation, asserting that in mathematics, a conjecture involves an attempt to establish a particular mathematical property without definitive proof. It remains applicable without conclusive disproof and often guides further research and exploration in the field. A conjecture is similar to a hypothesis, but unlike a hypothesis, it does not always need to be tested for a definite answer.

Similarly, the study reveals a high level of adaptive reasoning in terms of drawing the correct conclusion. This revealed that the level of adaptive reasoning of first-year students across all programs in terms of drawing the correct conclusion is oftentimes manifested. This indicates that drawing the correct conclusion exhibits a heightened ability to synthesize information, identify patterns, and extract deeper insights from the material they encounter. These are connected concepts that are essential to evaluate and solve complex problems.

This observation is supported by Urban and Wilson (2023), who stated that drawing conclusions is a fundamental skill in daily life. Individuals routinely make judgments based on what they observe, hear, or read, shaping their understanding of the world. Forming accurate conclusions involves making assessments or deductions based on the available information. In this context, students can improve their decision-making and problem-solving abilities, ultimately influencing their actions and outcomes.

In this connection, the findings are reinforced by the study of Lakha (2024). The study emphasized how students analyze results and draw meaningful conclusions within any math studies curriculum. Through this process, students understand the underlying principles behind scientific research and how to apply them in their studies. In this context, the ability of students to draw conclusions serves a

pivotal role in fostering analytical skills in students, not only in the field of mathematics but also in other disciplines.

Moreover, this is also supported by Kramer's study (2023), which stated that in the realm of diverse scientific disciplines, the ultimate juncture of any research endeavor is the drawing of conclusions. This critical stage ultimately determines the project's success or failure. The conclusion is a pivotal element regardless of the reasoning methods and research techniques employed. They possessed the authority to either affirm or undermine the overall credibility of the experiment.

In addition, the result identifies a high level of adaptive reasoning in terms of finding the correct pattern of a problem. This revealed that the level of adaptive reasoning of first-year students across all programs in terms of finding the correct pattern of a problem is oftentimes manifested. This indicates that finding the correct pattern of a problem is a methodology wherein students actively seek identifiable patterns within the given data to facilitate problem-solving. This ability helps students process information that could help them solve problems systematically and effectively.

This observation is corroborated by the study of Agarwal et al. (2023), which stated that identifying and extending patterns is integral to practical problem-solving. This involves the recognition of variations in attributes such as color, rotation, translation, shape, or size. This process, essential for analytical reasoning and mathematical proficiency, underscores the importance of pattern recognition in cognitive development. Moreover, the implications of this finding extend beyond individual problem-solving skills; it suggests that educational curricula and cognitive training programs should prioritize activities that enhance pattern recognition abilities to foster stronger analytical thinking and mathematical competence in learners.

In this connection, the finding is supported by the research of Zayyadi and Kurniat (2018), which revealed that students frequently relied on trial and error when identifying patterns, sometimes stumbling upon the correct one. However, their ability to recognize patterns often leans more towards intuition than being firmly grounded in a robust mathematical understanding. This underscores the need for educational approaches that encourage pattern recognition and foster deeper mathematical reasoning and proof skills to ensure a more comprehensive understanding among students.

Additionally, this is supported by the study of Cahyadi et al. (2023), which found that pattern-finding strategies are utilized in resolving mathematical problems concerning gender distinctions. The study revealed that both male and female students can identify and apply patterns in mathematical problem-solving. According to the outcomes, there is no discernible disparity in the proficiency of pattern-finding strategies between male and female students."

Moreover, the study reveals a high level of adaptive reasoning in terms of the presentation of correct reasoning. This revealed that the level of adaptive reasoning of first-year students across all programs in terms of the presentation of correct reasoning is oftentimes manifested. This indicates that these students may derive unique cognitive benefits from engaging in mathematical activities, and educators can leverage diverse strategies in teaching to enhance learning experiences for individuals with strong mathematical reasoning. Recognizing and fostering these skills contributes to a more holistic understanding of diverse mathematical problems within the educational setting.

This observation is consistent with the findings of Barton and Tucker (2021), who stated that having correct reasoning entails using evidence and logical thinking to reach valid and well-founded conclusions, serving as a crucial element in cognitive functions like effective communication, problem-solving, and critical thinking. These skills contribute to making informed decisions and building a more robust intellectual foundation. Thus, educators should incorporate activities that help students enhance their reasoning skills, essential in solving mathematical problems.

The results also correspond to the study by Wulandari and Wutsqa (2019), which explores the mathematical reasoning skills of junior high school students, focusing on analysis, generalization, synthesis, justification, and solution of non-routine problems. It was found that students exhibited commendable reasoning skills across diverse domains, indicating a promising trend in their mathematical abilities. Additionally, it was found that various factors were identified as influential on students' reasoning abilities, including their ability to recognize relevant information in the question and utilize mathematical arguments to clarify their answers. These students who exhibit strong reasoning skills are likely to excel in mathematics and other academic and real-world contexts where critical thinking and problem-solving abilities are essential.

In addition, this is further supported by the study by Masfingatini et al. (2020), which stated that creative mathematical reasoning involves a thought process encompassing elements of novelty, plausibility, and a solid mathematical foundation. Creative mathematical reasoning emerges when students engage in an algorithmic reasoning process but encounter situations where no solution is found.

Finally, the study identifies a high level of adaptive reasoning in terms of examining an argument. This revealed that the level of adaptive reasoning of first-year students across all programs in terms of examination of an argument is oftentimes observed. This indicates that the examination of arguments by these students may benefit from learning experiences that incorporate collaboration, interactive simulations, and experiential approaches, providing a more tailored and enriched educational experience. Recognizing and evaluating arguments can contribute to a more inclusive and effective educational environment that values diverse cognitive strengths.

This observation aligns with the findings of Reuter (2023), which investigate the explorative mathematical argumentation of students in their early phases of mathematical learning. This idea is a structure for comprehending and assessing how learners explore and

formulate mathematical arguments during their initial educational encounters. Furthermore, it underscores the significance of integrating collaborative, interactive, and experiential approaches to foster a deeper understanding of argumentation processes in mathematics and other disciplines.

The results also correspond to the study by Sengul and Altinel (2021), which examines how 10th-grade students approach problem-solving related to quadratic equations through argumentation. The study found that students who engage in the problem-solving process improve their understanding of the problems, enabling them to express their thoughts, persuade others of their perspectives, and communicate effectively. Additionally, they expressed a strong interest in participating in similar collaborative environments, indicating a desire for further engagement and learning opportunities.

This connection is also supported by Troolin (2023), who stated that evaluating an argument is a multifaceted process that requires carefully examining its logic, structure, and the strength of the evidence supporting a particular claim. To gauge the soundness and credibility of an argument, it is essential to scrutinize its components. This involves analyzing elements such as the main assertion, supporting reasons, presented evidence, and underlying assumptions.

Level of Mathematical Engagement

The respondents' level of mathematical engagement is generally high, as manifested by their active participation. This indicates that the student's mathematical engagement holds significant value. It underscores its pivotal role in fostering more profound understanding and proficiency in mathematical concepts and applications and emotional fulfillment from their mathematical learning experiences.

This idea is further supported by Al-Mutawah et al. (2018), who argue that student engagement in mathematics encompasses multiple facets, including emotional, cognitive, and behavioral elements. They also found that the level of students' involvement in their math education significantly influences the overall quality of their learning outcomes. Educators can use this insight to design teaching strategies catering to diverse learning styles and preferences in this context. By fostering an emotionally supportive classroom environment, they can encourage students to feel more positively disposed toward mathematics, enhancing their motivation and willingness to engage with the subject matter.

Additionally, this is further supported by the study of (Mentari and Syarifuddin, 2020), which suggests that the degree of student involvement in the learning process is delineated by three distinct realms: cognitive engagement, affective engagement, and behavioral engagement. They emphasize that teachers should identify the crucial variables that can contribute to active participation in their learning activities. With that in mind, providing top-notch educational resources and materials can boost student involvement and participation. Incorporating appropriate educational resources during the learning process promises to improve students' academic performance.

This connection is also supported by the study of Hartono et al. (2019), which analyzed the level of student engagement in history subjects among high school students in Jember, focusing on gender and class differences. The findings indicated a significant difference in student engagement levels based on gender and grade. The researchers suggested that educators should do proper learning planning by paying attention to differences in student characteristics to achieve learning goals.

Furthermore, the results indicate a high level of mathematical engagement in terms of cognitive engagement, which means that first-year students across all programs often manifest the indicator. This suggests that students have a strong intrinsic motivation to actively involve themselves in mathematical activities and challenges, potentially laying a solid foundation for their academic journey and future success in the field.

This confirms the study by Maloney (2023), which stated that students' cognitive engagement in the learning process is crucial for enhancing learning outcomes. This involvement stems from various activities, such as engaging in reading, writing, journaling, participating in dialogue, or problem-solving exercises, including using formulas in mathematics and algebra. It also emphasizes that engaging in active classroom involvement allows students to receive valuable assistance and feedback regarding their comprehension of the subject matter.

Bear et al. (2019) found that engaged students exhibit active attention, motivation, and enthusiasm in their studies. In contrast, disengaged peers often show signs of boredom, passivity, low motivation, and substandard academic performance. Furthermore, studies have indicated that students with elevated levels of engagement tend to maintain consistent attendance and achieve better academic results than their less-engaged counterparts. These findings underscore the importance of fostering student engagement in educational settings, as it enhances learning outcomes and contributes to improved attendance and academic achievement.

In this connection, this is supported by the study of Batool (2020), which examined the cognitive engagement of eighth-grade students in math classrooms. The results demonstrated a significant link between students' engagement levels and academic performance. Additionally, the study underscored gender variations in math achievement and cognitive engagement among students.

Additionally, the results indicate a high level of mathematical engagement in terms of affective engagement, meaning that first-year students across all programs often manifest the indicator. This indicates a consistent and frequent manifestation of contentment related to acquiring and applying mathematical skills. The high prevalence of affective engagement suggests that students perceive a

meaningful development of their mathematical abilities throughout their academic journey.

This connection is supported by the study of Maamin et al. (2021), which stated that students demonstrate affective engagement when they cultivate a sense of belonging within their educational institution, view themselves as integral members of the school community, and consider their school environment as a significant element of their personal experiences. The study also stated that the degree to which students feel connected to their educational institution significantly influences their motivation to complete tasks. Furthermore, affective engagement involves the emotional connection students establish with their mathematics courses and instructors. It was also emphasized that positive student-teacher relationships and effective communication have been shown to contribute to better academic outcomes. It parallels a study by Silva et al. (2021), which emphasizes the significance of students' affective engagement in achieving academic success and recommends that educational institutions employ methods to enhance well-being and discourage dropout. It also emphasizes the vital role of students' affective engagement in academic achievement and suggests that schools should implement approaches that foster well-being and mitigate dropout. This implies that directing attention toward students' affective engagement could aid schools in enhancing retention rates and overall academic success.

Similarly, this is corroborated by the study of Bowden et al. (2019), which emphasized the four crucial aspects of engagement: affective, social, cognitive, and behavioral. It explored how these dimensions impact both student and institutional success. Notably, affective engagement was the primary factor influencing institutional reputation, well-being, and transformative learning.

Moreover, the results indicate a high level of mathematical engagement in terms of behavioral engagement, which means that first-year students across all programs oftentimes manifest the indicator. This signifies that students consistently experience a sense of involvement and purpose in completing mathematical tasks and assignments, suggesting a robust commitment to their academic endeavors. Additionally, this high level of behavioral engagement underscores students' proactive approach toward their studies, demonstrating a deep-seated dedication to mastering mathematical concepts and skills essential for their academic success.

This confirms the study by Maat et al. (2021), which identified a noteworthy correlation between behavioral engagement and academic accomplishment. The study measured the level of diligence, which indicates one's behavioral engagement, and found that there are significant influences on academic performance. Based on the study, Effective practice and timely assignment submission influence the academic performance of diligent students. These characteristics are integral to students' behavioral engagement, reflecting their proactive approach toward learning and academic responsibilities.

This corresponds to the results of a study by Hidayat et al. (2019), which focused on the behavioral involvement of teenagers in mathematics courses. The study found a diminishing interest among students in school as they progressed through high school. Furthermore, it underscored the substantial influence of behavioral engagement on academic success, pointing out a noteworthy connection between engagement and mathematical achievement in the later years of elementary school.

It is parallel to a study by Wang et al. (2022), which examined the importance of students' aspirations to pursue mathematics-related coursework or careers beyond high school. These intentions are crucial in predicting behavioral engagement, which ultimately impacts performance in mathematics. Moreover, a positive correlation between behavioral engagement and mathematical performance has been identified, emphasizing the significance of students' aspirations.

Level of Learning Environment

The respondents' level of learning environment is generally high or oftentimes observed. This manifestation was evidenced by the respondents' responses to the questions in the research instrument. It further indicates that the student's learning environment places significant value on and facilitates successful learning in mathematical education. Students perceive their learning environment as conducive to studying, which can help them to excel academically.

This finding is further supported by Quiroga-Marabol et al. (2019), who stated that the educational environment is crucial in initiating improvements and ultimately elevating the educational setting. The comprehension of meaningful knowledge is intricately linked to how students perceive their learning environment, which influences their educational experiences and accomplishments. Furthermore, the learning environment significantly affects different facets of students' lives, encompassing their overall well-being, attitudes toward academic endeavors, and their ability to cope with the stress associated with educational programs.

This corresponds to a study by Smith and Johnson (2018), which stated that the learning environment plays a crucial role in shaping students' academic performance and overall educational experience. The study also found that classroom design influences students' perceptions of their learning surroundings. It was revealed that well-designed classrooms featuring adaptable seating arrangements and ample natural light positively influenced students' engagement and motivation levels.

This is further supported by the study of Brown et al. (2019), which investigated the impact of teacher-student relationships on students' perceptions of their educational environment. The findings revealed a noteworthy connection between favorable interactions among educators and students. These positive connections, characterized by elements like trust, respect, and effective communication, correlate significantly with elevated student satisfaction and engagement levels.

Furthermore, the result indicates a high level of motivation in the learning environment to exert learning effort. This revealed that the

level of learning environment of first-year students across all programs in terms of motivation to exert learning effort is oftentimes manifested. This indicates that the motivation to exert learning effort is crucial for fostering a conducive educational atmosphere and promoting academic success.

According to the study by Howley-Rouse (2023), motivation can be categorized as either intrinsic or extrinsic, and it can be influenced by factors such as the perceived value of the activity, individual goals, monetary rewards, and past learning experiences. It also stated that strong and adaptable critical thinking skills are nurtured by intrinsic motivation, whereas mere extrinsic motivation can result in diminished interest and academic perseverance. Hence, it is crucial to consider not just the degree of motivation a student exhibits but also the specific type of motivation they possess. Understanding these distinctions can enhance our approach to fostering a more effective learning environment.

Furthermore, this is supported by the study of Filgona et al. (2020), which stated that the effectiveness of learning is closely tied to the level of motivation exhibited by learners. Recognizing and cultivating motivation is a fundamental aspect of successful pedagogy. Learning demands significant mental effort, requiring the full utilization of cognitive capacities. Therefore, the acquisition of knowledge and skills relies on the presence of intrinsic or extrinsic motivation. The willingness of students to learn holds particular importance, especially in challenging subjects like mathematics, where mere attendance in the classroom does not guarantee active engagement. Learners with high motivation tend to grasp concepts more quickly, enhancing the overall teaching experience. Conversely, unmotivated learners may struggle with limited learning outcomes, making the teaching process challenging and frustrating.

This is also supported by the study of Dela Peña & Baluyos (2022), which explored the connection between students' intrinsic motivation and their proficiency in tackling mathematical challenges. The results revealed that, despite showcasing commendable problem-solving strategies and displaying heightened intrinsic motivation, students surprisingly exhibited lower-than-expected performance in mathematics. The study pinpointed students' approaches to solving word problems and motivational factors like interest, effort, and value as pivotal contributors to their overall mathematical performance.

Additionally, the results determined that the level of the learning environment in terms of activate towards self-regulated learning is high. This indicates that first-year students across all programs consistently demonstrate a high level of activation toward self-regulated learning in their learning environment. This indicates that the activate towards self-regulated learning of students plays a significant role in fostering independent and effective learning practices, thereby contributing to their academic success and overall educational experience.

According to Fauzi and Widjajanti (2018), self-regulated learning is a vital skill for students, especially in mathematics education. The study found that those with a strong capacity for self-regulated learning typically exhibit heightened motivation and academic success, unlike their counterparts with lower self-regulation, who tend to struggle academically. These findings underscore the importance of fostering self-regulated learning skills to enhance students' academic performance and overall educational experience.

The research study by Dignath and Veenman (2020) proposes a framework outlining the activation of self-regulated learning (SRL) both directly through strategy instruction and indirectly through creating a conducive learning environment enabling students to regulate their own learning. The findings underscore the importance of explicitly teaching SRL strategies, allowing students to develop metacognitive knowledge and skills for successful integration into their learning process. This highlights the significance of educators facilitating an optimal learning environment and providing structured guidance on self-regulatory techniques to empower students in their academic journey.

Similarly, this is also supported by the statement of Wang et al. (2020), which asserted that for students to become self-regulated learners in mathematics, it is essential to provide them with opportunities to express and critically analyze their cognitive processes. Additionally, individuals should be capable of actively participating in observing, critically analyzing, and modeling the cognitive processes used by others.

Additionally, the results determined that the level of the learning environment in terms of feedback and coaching is high. This reveals that the level of the learning environment of first-year students across all programs in terms of feedback and coaching is oftentimes manifested. This indicates that providing effective feedback and coaching to students is crucial for their academic development and overall learning experience.

In the study by Fry (2021), it is defined that effective feedback and coaching are pivotal in acquiring and enhancing mathematical skills. In mathematics education, the feedback given to students must go beyond mere assessment of answer correctness, embracing a more holistic approach. Teachers play a vital role in guiding students to grasp grade-level knowledge by offering feedback and encouraging independent learning and progress. This emphasizes the importance of feedback in assessing students' understanding and fostering their growth and development as mathematicians.

It is further supported by the article by Chiappetta (2022), which states that using positive feedback in math classrooms emphasizes the importance of providing constructive feedback in math education. It also states that instead of simply marking correct answers, teachers can use feedback to communicate values, strengths, areas for growth, and further learning opportunities to students. Positive feedback

in math classrooms can reinforce essential qualities like clarity, logic, creativity, perseverance, and curiosity. By strategically using positive feedback, educators can enhance students' understanding, motivation, and engagement in mathematics.

Similarly, this is confirmed by the statement of Loman et al. (2019), which highlighted that incorporating peer coaching into teacher education programs underscores its favorable influence on the professional development of teacher candidates. Additionally, participation in peer coaching experiences enables teacher candidates to nurture critical skills, notably reflective practice, with practical applications in their prospective teaching careers.

Finally, the result determined that the level of the learning environment in terms of structure and steer is very high. This reveals that the level of the learning environment for first-year students across all programs, in terms of structure and steer, is always manifested. This indicates that a well-managed environment can significantly contribute to students' performance and enjoyment of learning experiences. Additionally, it underscores the importance of educators and institutions prioritizing the creation of well-structured and guided learning environments to enhance students' academic performance and overall satisfaction with their learning journey.

In addition, this is consistent with the results of Tremblay-Wragg et al.'s (2019) study, which found that structured learning environments can indeed enhance student motivation. The perception of the learning environment is as effective on the learning outcomes as the structuring of the learning environment. This implies that when students are provided with clear frameworks, an organized curriculum, and well-defined goals, they are more likely to feel motivated to engage with the learning process. Structured learning environments often provide students with a sense of direction and purpose, which can increase their intrinsic motivation. Additionally, clear expectations and guidelines can reduce feelings of confusion or uncertainty, leading to a more positive learning experience.

In keeping with Lee (2019), who suggests that a positive and collaborative atmosphere contributes significantly to the overall learning experience, this additional dimension reinforces the idea that successful learning environments extend beyond individual adaptations, physical spaces, and technology integration, emphasizing the social context as a crucial determinant of educational success. Therefore, educators should consider not only the individual needs of students but also the social interactions within the learning environment to create truly holistic and effective educational spaces.

Additionally, this is supported by the statement of Cummings (2022), which described structured education as a pedagogical approach characterized by its emphasis on visual aids that facilitate comprehensive comprehension of expected outcomes, instructional tasks, and schedules within a well-organized setting. Structured learning helps develop students' behavior management, communication, and social skills. The presence of structure and guidance within a learning environment is a significant element that can influence the overall learning experience of students.

Relationship between Adaptive Reasoning and Mathematical Engagement

The outcome demonstrates a strong correlation between adaptive reasoning and mathematical engagement. This suggests that possessing strong reasoning skills may increase students' engagement in mathematics and potentially affect their overall happiness with their mathematical education. Next, it's important to validate Spiro et al.'s cognitive flexibility theory (1987), which defines that certain mathematical concepts and problem-solving tasks of students with a mathematics focus on the nature of learning in complex and ill-structured domains. The theory emphasizes the ability to spontaneously restructure one's knowledge in various ways in adaptive response to radically changing situational demands. This ability can significantly enhance students' mathematical engagement, promoting a deeper understanding and appreciation of the subject.

Moreover, the findings also showed that adaptive reasoning denotes the capacity to engage in flexible thinking, empowering individuals to analyze problems from diverse perspectives and devise successful solutions. Within an academic context, this skill empowers students to address complex challenges by adjusting their cognitive strategies to match the demands of the task. An experimental group has exhibited significant progress in adaptive reasoning, as highlighted by the study's outcomes. The findings indicated that students in this group exhibit logical thinking in their selection of appropriate concepts, procedural materials, and the application of formulas to solve problems Lestari et al. (2020).

As a result, researchers found that students with strong reasoning skills can correctly apply their own reasoning to solve problems, making logical connections based on known facts and paying attention to whether the procedures followed adhere to applicable rules. Reid (2018) suggests that adaptive reasoning involves thinking logically about the relationship between concepts and programs, generalizing them meaningfully to solve problems in a reasonable manner. Thus, improving students' adaptive reasoning skills not only helps in solving current mathematical problems but also prepares them for future, more complex challenges by fostering a deeper understanding of mathematical principles.

A research study by Frabasilio (2022) asserted that adaptive reasoning is one of five components students use to develop mathematical expertise and become mathematically proficient. When students adapt their reasoning, they logically think about the mathematical relationships between concepts and adapt their thinking to solve problems. Additionally, cultivating adaptive reasoning skills in students can greatly enhance their ability to tackle complex mathematical problems, leading to increased engagement and improved overall mathematical proficiency. It is crucial to include adaptive reasoning exercises and activities in the teaching methods to create

a more dynamic and effective learning environment.

Relationship between Adaptive Reasoning and Learning Environment

In addition, the correlation analysis showed a significant relationship between the learning environment and adaptive reasoning. To optimize learning results, this implies that developing a conducive learning environment can support the improvement of reasoning skills. The results of this research support Lev Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (1896–1934). According to the ZPD, learning occurs optimally within the ZPD, promoting cognitive growth through tasks that are slightly challenging for the learner. A conducive learning environment, active engagement, and individualized support not only guide and inspire students to adopt more effective learning strategies but also provide them with the tools and motivation to navigate and adapt their strategies, resulting in more successful and meaningful learning experiences. A conducive learning environment can encourage and equip students to select and apply the most suitable learning strategies for their goals. As a result, students in these environments are more likely to engage with their studies more efficiently, adapt their strategies when needed, and achieve a deeper understanding and mastery of the subject matter.

In connection with this, a research study endorsed by Sánchez-Barbero et al. (2020) concluded that in order to create an effective mathematics learning environment, teachers must pose interventions based on non-traditional (non-routine) mathematical tasks to facilitate and increase classroom interaction. Furthermore, it was found that non-traditional mathematical tasks enhance classroom interaction, as they present challenges for both teachers and students when dealt with in the classroom.

Moreover, Hegseth (2021) reported that when the teacher works on establishing a classroom environment of mutual respect and focuses on standards of classroom interaction in mathematics classes, students become more likely to engage effectively in class discussions and verbal interactions, thereby improving their mathematical skills. This underscores the importance of fostering a supportive and interactive learning atmosphere in mathematics education.

Furthermore, Becker et al. (2018) stated that physical environments in educational institutions demand modification to better align with contemporary pedagogical practices that emphasize the active role of students in the learning process. These changes are essential to creating flexible and dynamic learning spaces that support collaboration, creativity, and hands-on activities. By redesigning learning spaces to promote active learning, students are better positioned to develop and apply adaptive reasoning skills. This approach fosters a deeper understanding of mathematical principles through problem-solving and critical thinking, aligning physical spaces with the demands of modern education.

Relationship between Learning Environment and Mathematical Engagement

The correlation test, which acts as a navigational compass, revealed a significant relationship between the learning environment and mathematical engagement. This points out that to improve students' performance in mathematics education, educators must design learning environments conducive to active participation and meaningful learning experiences. This study confirms the Self-Determination Theory of Ryan and Deci (2000), which emphasizes the satisfaction of basic human needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness as key drivers of motivated behavior. According to SDT, intrinsically motivating tasks are interesting, enjoyable, and spontaneously pursued by individuals. Such motivation is experienced as autonomous and self-determined. Therefore, SDT describes several different types of extrinsic motivation. External regulation is the least internalized form of extrinsic motivation, with individuals pursuing tasks because of rewards or punishments present in the environment. Therefore, when students perceive their learning environment as supportive of their autonomy, they are more likely to engage intrinsically in tasks, including mathematics.

Additionally, a research study found that in environments where students feel supported by teachers and peers, they are more engaged, develop closer relationships, are less fearful of making mistakes, and put forth more significant effort (Lazarides et al., 2019). Furthermore, the findings underscore the critical role of fostering a supportive and encouraging atmosphere in educational settings, as it enhances student engagement and relationships and promotes resilience and a willingness to take academic risks.

Moreover, the findings also showed that, given the nature of mathematics, which requires special learning efforts by students to reach a high or at least an acceptable level of mathematical proficiency, teachers must select the best strategies and methods to assist their students. Investing in any classroom setting in the teaching process is essential to enable students to acquire mathematical concepts, master mathematical skills, justify mathematical settings, and reflect on their solutions to problems presented to them (Larrain & Kaiser, 2022).

Further, Morieson et al. (2018) highlight the significance of offering convenient, comfortable, and quiet places where students can focus on studying. These environments are essential for promoting concentration and practical learning. In addition, creating such spaces can enhance students' academic performance, mathematics engagement, and overall well-being by minimizing distractions and fostering a friendly environment for studying.

Mediating Role of Learning Environment on The Relationship Between Adaptive Reasoning and Mathematics Engagement Among First Year Students Across All Programs

The results of the mediation computation revealed that the learning environment partially mediates the relationship between adaptive reasoning and mathematical engagement. This suggests that the learning environment's inclusion can influence the relationship between

adaptive reasoning and mathematical engagement.

Furthermore, the results confirm Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (1986). According to social cognitive theory, learning occurs in a social context with a dynamic and reciprocal interaction of the person, environment, and behavior. The theory emphasizes social influence and external and internal social reinforcement. It also considers the unique ways individuals acquire and maintain behavior while considering the social environment in which they perform it. This suggests that exposure to diverse perspectives, opportunities for critical reflection, and engagement in problem-solving activities can enhance reasoning skills. Additionally, educators should design learning experiences and environments conducive to challenging students to analyze complex problems, consider multiple viewpoints, and apply creative solutions, contributing to their engagement in mathematics and overall academic success.

In line with this, the findings also confirmed the claim of Cain (2019), which states that an active learning environment increases pupils' motivation and engagement and fosters learning while using or developing teamwork and communication skills. Learners appreciate the diversity of puzzles of a problem-solving and discovery nature, as well as the need for physical attributes and collaboration. Furthermore, learners described being more active, needing to think more thoroughly than in a regular lesson, and enjoying the feeling of autonomy.

Similarly, the research findings, as stated by Casanova et al. (2018), indicate that students and professors have historically had limited involvement in developing learning spaces for higher education. Similarly, the literature indicates that it is essential to view and assess learning settings from students' standpoint, highlighting the necessity for a greater focus on student views. Engaging students in the design process can significantly improve their reasoning skills and encourage active involvement in mathematics. This can enhance critical thinking and logical reasoning abilities, leading to a more profound comprehension and appreciation of mathematical concepts.

Moreover, Aluri and Fraser (2019) found that teacher support and involvement significantly predicted students' math scores. This finding highlights the importance of a supportive learning environment in fostering mathematical achievement. The role of teachers extends beyond mere instruction to actively engaging with students, providing encouragement, and creating a classroom atmosphere conducive to learning. Their involvement can help build students' confidence, motivate them to tackle challenging problems and enhance their mathematical performance.

Conclusions

This section consists of the overall summary of the study, particularly the results and each of their implications. Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn in answer to the objectives:

The level of adaptive reasoning, as perceived by first-year students across all programs, is high in terms of the proposition of the correct conjecture, drawing the correct conclusion, finding the correct pattern of a problem, presentation of correct reasoning, and examination of an argument. Thus, fostering teaching approaches such as collaborative learning, as perceived by students, empowers them to improve their reasoning skills, actively engage in the learning process, and enhance their ability to comprehend and apply knowledge effectively.

Additionally, the level of mathematical engagement among first-year students across all programs in terms of cognitive, affective, and behavioral engagement is high. Thus, cultivating engagement in mathematics learning enables students to increase performance. Additionally, increasing mathematical engagement encourages a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts, enhances problem-solving skills, and promotes critical thinking abilities.

Furthermore, the level of the learning environment among first-year students across all programs in terms of motivation to exert learning effort, activate towards self-regulated learning, and feedback and coach are all high. On the other hand, the structure and steer are at a very high level. Thus, designing conducive learning environments empowers students to engage more deeply with the subject, fosters collaboration, and promotes a sense of belonging and motivation, particularly in mathematics.

The findings show a significant relationship between adaptive reasoning and mathematical engagement. The understanding that adaptive reasoning in learning is more likely to influence mathematical engagement in a broad context affirms this. Thus, according to students' perceptions, adaptive reasoning greatly influences their level of mathematical engagement, emphasizing the significance of the relationship between these two variables.

The study also revealed a significant relationship between adaptive reasoning and the learning environment. Consequently, students' perceptions of their learning environment and adaptive reasoning mutually reinforce each other throughout their mathematics learning process. Hence, according to students' perspectives, adaptive reasoning is greatly influenced by their learning environment, further underscoring the significant relationship between these two variables.

Moreover, researchers found a significant relationship between the learning environment and mathematical engagement. Consequently, students emphasize conducive learning environments when they view intellectual thinking and mathematical ability as areas they can enhance through effort and study. Thus, students' learning environment significantly influences their level of mathematical engagement, highlighting the substantial relationship between these two variables.

Finally, the mediation analysis revealed that the learning environment has partially mediated the relationship between adaptive reasoning and mathematical engagement. Therefore, the conducive learning environment in mathematics is intricately intertwined with the interplay of adaptive reasoning, mathematical engagement, and the design of a positive learning environment, collectively shaping the educational landscape and influencing students' academic achievements and overall mathematical proficiency. However, in the context of the results, they stipulate that the indirect pathway partially mediates the relationship between adaptive reasoning and mathematical engagement through the learning environment, a claim that is also supported by the estimation of a significant indirect effect.

The suggestions of the researcher are established based on the results and the wholeness of the paper. In light of the findings above of the study, the following recommendations were made:

The level of adaptive reasoning perceived by first-year students across all programs is high. However, among the items of each indicator of adaptive reasoning, it was found that drawing the correct conclusion was the item with the lowest mean result. Therefore, these students may request more appropriate learning activities to help improve their ability to draw correct conclusions. Teachers may employ exercises or activities requiring students to analyze information, identify patterns, and make logical conclusions to arrive at reasoned conclusions. Additionally, incorporating real-world examples can help students see the practical application of drawing conclusions in various contexts.

Moreover, the level of mathematical engagement among first-year students across all programs is high. However, the study revealed that affective engagement had the lowest mean results among all the indicators of mathematical engagement. Therefore, teachers may search for activities and teaching strategies that can motivate these students to engage more in mathematics and boost their interest in the subject. By nurturing positive attitudes and emotional connections, students can enhance their overall mathematical experience and potentially improve their performance and persistence in their academic journey.

Furthermore, the level of the learning environment among first-year students across all programs is high. However, among the items of each indicator of the learning environment, it was found that activate towards self-regulated learning and feedback and coach were the items with the lowest mean results. Therefore, these students may benefit from implementing strategies that promote self-regulated learning and increase opportunities for receiving constructive feedback and coaching. These approaches can empower students to take control of their learning process, set goals, monitor their progress, and adapt their strategies accordingly, ultimately enhancing their academic performance and overall learning experience.

Finally, as the learning environment partially mediates the relationship between adaptive reasoning and mathematical engagement, it is recommended that future researchers investigate other variables that could fully mediate the relationship between adaptive reasoning and mathematical engagement throughout the learning of mathematics. They are encouraged to utilize other methodologies, factors, or variables the study could not cover. Additionally, they might conduct it in other locales and with larger-scale participants.

References

- Abín, A., Núñez, J. C., Rodríguez, C., Cueli, M., García, T., and Rosário, P. (2020). Predicting mathematics achievement in secondary education: the role of cognitive, motivational, and emotional variables. *Front. Psychol.* 11:876. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00876
- Agarwal, H., Jain, M., and Parra Vega, H.A., (2023). Recognizing Visual Patterns | Brilliant Math & Science Wiki. (n.d.). <https://brilliant.org/wiki/pattern-recognition-visual-easy-2/>
- Al-Mutawah, M. A., & Fateel, M. J. (2018). Students' achievement in math and science: How grit and attitudes influence? *International Education Studies*, 11(2), 97-105. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ies.v11n2p97>
- Aluri, V. L. N., & Fraser, B. J. (2019). Students' perceptions of mathematics classroom learning environments: Measurement and associations with achievement. *Learning Environments Research*, 22(3), 409-426.
- Ansari, B. I., & Sulastri, R. (2018). Validation of prototype instruments for implementing higher-order thinking learning using the IMPROVE method. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1088(1), 012113.
- Ansari, B. I., Taufiq, Saminan, (2020). The use of creative problem-solving model to develop students' adaptive reasoning ability: Inductive, deductive, and intuitive
file:///C:/Users/Administrator/Downloads/The_use_of_creative_problem_solving_model_to_devel.pdf
- Asino T., Pulay A., (2019). Student perceptions on the role of the classroom environment on computer supported collaborative learning.
- Ayub, A. F. M., Suraya, A., Mahmud, R., and Salim, N. R., (2017). Differences in students' mathematics engagement between gender and between rural and urban schools
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/312208917_Differences_in_students'_mathematics_engagement_between_gender_and_between_rural_and_urban_schools
- Bandura A. (1986). *Social foundations of thought and action: A social cognitive theory*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.

Barlow, A. J., Brown, S., Lutz, B. D., Pitterson, N. P., Hunsu, N. J., & Adesope, O. (2020). Development of the student course cognitive engagement instrument (SCCEI) for college engineering courses. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-020-00220-9>

Barton, K., & Tucker, B., (2021). What is Correct Reasoning? [https://socialsci.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Communication/Public_Speaking/Exploring_Public_Speaking_4e_\(Barton_and_Tucker\)/14%3A_Logical_Reasoning/14.01%3A_What_is_Correct_Reasoning](https://socialsci.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Communication/Public_Speaking/Exploring_Public_Speaking_4e_(Barton_and_Tucker)/14%3A_Logical_Reasoning/14.01%3A_What_is_Correct_Reasoning)

Batool, T. (2020). Investigating cognitive engagement of eighth graders in mathematics classrooms. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Investigating-Cognitive-Engagement-of-Eighth-in-Batool-Akhtar/a2c0de7e2f8bd41a7720bc8f85d721bef8a184ca>

Bear, G.G., Yang, C., Chen, D., He, X., Xie, J.S., & Huang, X. (2018). Differences in school climate and student engagement in China and the United States. *School Psychology Quarterly*, 33(2), 323-335. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/spq0000247>.

Becker, S., Brown, M., Dahlstrom, E., Davis, A., DePaul, K., Diaz, V., et al. (2018). NMC Horizon report: 2018 higher (education ed.). Louisville, CO: EDUCAUSE.

Becker, S., Kuchemann, S., Klein, P., Lichtenberger, A., and Kuhn, A., (2022). Gaze patterns enhance response prediction: More than correct or incorrect <https://www.per-central.org/items/detail.cfm?ID=16180>

Beckers, R. (2019). Learning space design in higher education. In K. Fisher (Ed.), *The translational design of universities*. (pp. 194–175). BrillSense. 10.1163/9789004391598_010.

Bennett, T. A., & Boesdorfer, S. B. (2020). Coupling PhET simulations and POGIL: High school chemistry students' learning and engagement in argumentation on the topic of atomic theory. *Journal of Teacher Action Research*, 6(2), 26–53.

Blanco, J. (2023, July 7). How to best handle conflicts of interest in Research | Orvium. Orvium. <https://blog.orvium.io/conflict-of-interest-in-research/>

Blogger, G. (2020, October 7). How motivation affects learning. *The Inspired Classroom*. <https://theinspiredclassroom.com/2013/07/how-motivation-affects-learning/>

Bowden, J., Tickle, L., & Naumann, K. (2019). The four pillars of tertiary student engagement and success: a holistic measurement approach. *Studies in Higher Education*, 46(6), 1207–1224. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2019.1672647>

Bronkhorst, H., Roorda, G., Suhre, C., & Goedhart, M. (2020a). Logical reasoning in formal and everyday reasoning tasks. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 18(8), 1673–1694. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10763-019-10039-8>

Brown, C., Lewis R. (2019). Teacher-Student Relationships: Examining Their Influence on Students' Perceptions of Learning Environment. *Educational Research Quarterly*, 36(2), 123-136.

Cahyadi, M. R., Ariansyah, F., & da Silva Santiago, P. V., (2023). Analysis of skills using pattern-finding strategies in solving mathematical problems given gender differences https://www.researchgate.net/publication/374914778_Analysis_of_skills_using_pattern-finding_strategies_in_solving_mathematical_problems_given_gender_differences

Cambaya E. and Tan D. (2022) "ENHANCING STUDENTS' PROBLEM-SOLVING SKILLS AND ENGAGEMENT IN MATHEMATICS LEARNING THROUGH CONTEXTUALIZED INSTRUCTION" Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/359437542_ENHANCING_STUDENTS'_PROBLEM_SOLVING_SKILLS_AND_ENGAGEMENT_IN_MATHEMATICS_LEARNING_THROUGH_CONTEXTUALIZED_INSTRUCTION

Casanova, D., Di Napoli, R., & Leijon, M. (2018). Which space? Whose space? An experience in involving students and teachers in space design. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 23(4), 488–503.

Chiappetta, E., (2022). Using Positive Feedback in Math Classrooms <https://www.edutopia.org/article/using-positive-feedback-math-classrooms/>

Collie, R. J., Martin, A. J., Bobis, J., Way, J., & Anderson, J. (2019). How students switch on and switch off in mathematics: Exploring patterns and predictors of (dis) engagement across middle school and high school. *Educational Psychology*, 39(4), 489–509

Da Silva, C. R., Veiga, F. H., Pinto, É. S., & Ferreira, I. (2021). Retention in school. *DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals)*. <https://doi.org/10.29352/mill0214.20277>

Daher, W., Sabbah, K., & Abuzant, M. (2021). Affective engagement of higher education students in an online course. *Emerging Science Journal*, 5(4), 545–558. <https://doi.org/10.28991/esj-2021-01296>

Davao E. (2012). Kapalong College: Davao Region's first recognized municipal college. Retrieved from:

<https://edgedavao.net/suburbia/2012/01/01/kapalongncollege-davaoregions-first-recognized-municipal-college/>

Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2008). Self-determination theory: A macrotheory of human motivation, development, and health. *Canadian Psychology / Psychologie canadienne*, 49(3), 182–185. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0012801>

Dela Peña, L., & Baluyos, G. (2022). Intrinsic Motivation as Predictor of Students' Mathematics Problem-Solving Performance. <https://uijrt.com/articles/v4/i1/UIJRTV4I10009.pdf>

Denzin, N., & Lincoln, Y. (2011). *The Sage handbook of qualitative research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE. <https://books.google.com.ph/>

Dewi, K., Waluya, S. B., Rachmad, & Firmasari, S. (2020). Adaptive reasoning and procedural fluency in three-dimensional. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1511.

Dignath, C., & Veenman, M. V. J. (2020). The role of direct strategy instruction and indirect activation of self-regulated learning—evidence from classroom observation studies. *Educational Psychology Review*, 33(2), 489–533. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-020-09534-0>

El-Adl, A. & Alkharusi, H. (2020). Relationships between self-regulated learning strategies, learning motivation and mathematics achievement. *Cypriot Journal of Educational Science*, 15(1), 104–111. <https://doi.org/10.18844/cjes.v15i1.4461>

Fauzi, A., & Widjajanti, D. B. (2018). Self-regulated learning: the effect on student's mathematics achievement. *Journal of Physics*, 1097, 012139. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1097/1/012139>

Filgona J. Sakiyo J., Gwany D M., Okoronka A U., (2020), “Motivation in Learning” Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344199983_Motivation_in_Learning

Fisher, D., Kusumah, Y. S., & Dahlan, J. A. (2019). Junior high school students' mathematical reasoning ability analysis in systems of linear equations and applications. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1315, 012044. <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/1315/1/012044/pdf>

Fisher, K. (Ed.). (2019). *The translational design of universities: An evidence-based approach to aligning pedagogy and learning environments*. Sense Publishers.

Frabasilio, A. (2022). Relationships Between Middle School Students' Adaptive Reasoning When Creating Learner-Generated Drawings and Partner Talk During Inquiry-Based Mathematical Tasks <https://digitalcommons.usu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=9659&context=et>

Frenzel, A. C., Pekrun, R., & Goetz, T. (2007). Perceived learning environment and students' emotional experiences: A multilevel analysis of mathematics classrooms. *Learning and Instruction*, 17(5), 478-493.

Greenwood, B. (2020). Understanding Pedagogy - What is Social Constructivism? <https://blog.teamsatchel.com/what-is-social-constructivism>

Hadijah, H., Isnarto, I., & Walid, W. (2022b). The effect of immediate feedback on mathematics learning achievement. *Jurnal Pijar Matematika Dan Ilmu Pengetahuan Alam*, 17(6), 712–716. <https://doi.org/10.29303/jpm.v17i6.4172>

Hartono, F.P., Umamah, N., & Sumarno, R.P.N.P. (2019). The level of student engagement based on gender and grade on history subject of senior high school students in Jember Regency. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/266d/8bfab53c186e423d9fe03acaf69ab5983f4c.pdf>.

Hidayah, I. N., Sa'dijah, C., Subanji, S., & Sudirman, S. (2021). The students' cognitive engagement in online mathematics learning in the pandemic Covid-19 era. *Nucleation and Atmospheric Aerosols*. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0043567>

Hidayat, D., Kim, T., Listiani, T., & Setianingsih, A. R. (2019). Adolescence Student Behavioral Engagement in Mathematics Class <https://ejournal.undiksha.ac.id/index.php/JPI/article/view/16927/14633>

Howley-Rouse, A. (2023, October 11). The role of motivation in learning. *THE EDUCATION HUB*. <https://theeducationhub.org.nz/motivation/>

Iksan Z., Maat S., Maamin M., (2021) “The Influence of Student Engagement on Mathematical Achievement among Secondary School Students” Retrieved from: <https://www.mdpi.com/2227-7390/10/1/41>

Inayah, S., Septian, A., & Fazrianto, R. (2020). Student Procedural Fluency in Numerical Method Subjects. *Desimal: Jurnal Matematika* Vol 3 No 1 (2020), 53-64. <https://doi.org/10.24042/djm.v3i1.5316>

Jhangiani, R., Chiang, I-C., Cuttler, C., & Leighton, D., (2019). Drawing Conclusions and Reporting the Results <https://kpu.pressbooks.pub/psychmethods4e/chapter/drawing-conclusions-and-reporting-the-results/>

- Joseph, (2021). What Is Conjecture in Mathematics? <https://www.superprof.co.uk/blog/maths-conjecture-and-hypotheses/>
- Joshi, D. R., Adhikari, K. P., Khanal, B., Khadka, J., & Belbase, S., (2022). Behavioral, cognitive, emotional and social engagement in mathematics learning during COVID-19 pandemic <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9681528/>
- Kilpatrick J, Swafford J, and Findell B 2001 Adding It Up: Helping Children Learn Mathematics (Washington, DC National Academy Press)
- Kiuhara, S., Levin, J., Tolbert, M., O’Keeffe, B., O’Neill, R., & Jameson, J.M., (2023). Teaching argument writing in math class: challenges and solutions to improve the performance of 4th and 5th graders with disabilities <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC10251315/>
- Kramer, P. (2023). Icono: a universal language that shows what it says. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, 1149381. doi:10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1149381
- Kwong, H., (2021, February 6). 2.6 Arguments and rules of inference. Mathematics LibreTexts. https://math.libretexts.org/Courses/Monroe_Community_College/MTH_220_Discrete_Math/2%3A_Logic/2.6_Arguments_and_Rules_of_Inference
- Layco, E., (2020). Enhancing The Self-Regulated Learning Skills and Mathematical Performance using Zimmermans SRL Model https://www.researchgate.net/publication/346203616_Enhancing_The_Self-Regulated_Learning_Skills_and_Mathematical_Performance_using_Zimmermans_SRL_Model
- Lazarides, R., Gaspard, H., & Dicke, A. L. (2019). Dynamics of classroom motivation: Teacher enthusiasm and the development of math interest and teacher support. *Learning and Instruction*, 60, 126–137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2018.01.012>
- Lee, S. (2020). The Influence of Technology Integration on Students’ Perceptions of Learning Environment. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 45(1), 56-68.
- Lee, Y., Capraro, R. M., & Biçer, A. (2019). Affective Mathematics Engagement: a Comparison of STEM PBL Versus Non-STEM PBL Instruction. *Canadian Journal of Science, Mathematics and Technology Education*, 19(3), 270–289. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42330-019-00050-0>
- Lestari, D. I., Waluya, S. B., & Mulyono. (2020). Mathematical literacy ability and self-efficacy students in search solve create and share (sscs) learning with contextual approaches. *Unnes Journal of Mathematics Education Research*, 9(2), 156–162.
- Loman, K., Nickens, N., Tye, N., Danley, A., Snider, K., McCoy, A., Diekmann, S., & Gilbert, A. (2019). Peer coach during field experiences: cultivating teacher candidates’ peer feedback and reflective practices. *Journal of Early Childhood Teacher Education*, 41(1), 85–99. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10901027.2019.1569183>
- MacKinnon, D., Fairchild, A., and Fritz, M., (2007). Mediation Analysis <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2819368/>
- Maloney (2023) “20 Best Student Engagement Strategies for Math Teachers” Retrieved from: <https://www.bytelearn.com/articles/best-student-engagement-strategies/>
- Martyn Shuttleworth, Lyndsay T Wilson (Jul 22, 2008). Drawing Conclusions. Retrieved Nov 23, 2023 from Explorable.com: <https://explorable.com/drawing-conclusions>
- Masfingat, T., Murtafiah, W., & Maharani, S. (2020). Exploration of Creative Mathematical Reasoning in Solving Geometric Problems https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343393067_Exploration_of_Creative_Mathematical_Reasoning_in_Solving_Geometric_Problems
- McKenney, S., & Reeves, T. C. (2019). *Conducting educational design research* (2nd ed.). Routledge.
- Mcleod, S., PhD. (2023). Vygotsky’s Zone of Proximal Development and Scaffolding Theory. *Simply Psychology*. <https://www.simplypsychology.org/zone-of-proximal-development.html>
- McMinn, M., Aldridge, J. M., & Henderson, D. (2020). Learning environment, self-efficacy for teaching mathematics, and beliefs about mathematics. *Learning Environments Research*, 24(3), 355–369. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10984-020-09326-x>
- Mentari W N., Syarifuddin H., (2020) “Improving student engagement by mathematics learning based on contextual teaching and learning” Retrieved from: <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/1554/1/012003/pdf>
- Moliner, L., and Alegre, F. (2020). Peer tutoring effects on students’ mathematics anxiety: a middle school experience. *Front. Psychol.* 11:1610. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.01610
- Morieson, L., Murray, G., Wilson, R., Clarke, B., & Lucas, K. (2018). Belonging in space: Informal learning spaces and student

experience. *Journal of Learning Spaces*, 7(2), 12–22

Mullis, I., Martin, M., Foy, P., Kelly, D., & Fishbein, B. (2019). TIMSS 2019 international results in mathematics and science. TIMSS & PIRLS International Study Center, Lynch School of Education and Human Development, Boston College and International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA), 9

Nelwan, M., Vissers, C., & Kroesbergen, E. H. (2018). Coaching positively influences the effects of working memory training on visual working memory as well as mathematical ability. *Neuropsychologia*, 113, 140–149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropsychologia.2018.04.002>

OECD. (2019). Programme for international students' assessment (PISA) results from PISA 2018. OECD 2019, 1(3), 1-12. https://www.oecd.org/pisa/publications/PISA2018_CN_PHL.pdf

Pagán (2018). "Behavioral, Affective, and Cognitive Engagement of High School Music Students: Relation to Academic Achievement and Ensemble Performance Ratings". USF Tampa Graduate Theses and Dissertations. <https://digitalcommons.usf.edu/etd/7347>

Price, P., Jhangiani, R., & Chiang, I. (2014). *Research Methods in Psychology - 2nd Canadian Edition*. California State University, Fresno: Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International License.

Pyne, J. (2020). Gender Test Score Gaps under Equal Behavioral Engagement. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1265855>

Ravelli, L. (2018). Towards a social-semiotic topography of learning spaces: Tools to connect use, users, and meanings. In R.A. Ellis and P. Goodyear (Eds.), *Spaces of teaching and learning: Integrating perspectives on teaching and research* (pp. 63–80). Springer. <https://www.springer.com/gp/book/9789811071546>

Razzaq, R., Ostrow, K., & Heffernan, N., (2020). Effect of Immediate Feedback on Math Achievement at the High School Level https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-52240-7_48

Reuter, F. (2023). Explorative mathematical argumentation: a theoretical framework for identifying and analysing argumentation processes in early mathematics learning. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 112(3), 415–435. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10649-022-10199-5>

Richardson, D. S., Bledsoe, R. S., & Cortez, Z. (2020). Mindset, Motivation, and Teaching Practice: Psychology applied to understanding teaching and learning in STEM disciplines. *CBE- Life Sciences Education*, 19(3), ar46. <https://doi.org/10.1187/cbe.19-11-0238>

Rustana, C. E., & Sumantri, M. F. (2019). The analysis of mathematical adaptive reasoning (pam) and scientific literacy on the 10th grade students' understanding of physics concepts. *AIP Conference Proceedings*, 2169. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5132642>

San Juan, R. (2019). Deped welcomes PISA results, recognizes 'gaps' in education quality. PhilStar global. <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2019/12/04/1974229/depedwelcomes-pisa-resultsrecognizes-gaps-education-quality>

Sánchez-Barbero, B., Chamoso, J., Vicente, S., & Rosales, J. (2020). Analysis of teacher-student interaction in the joint solving of non-routine problems in primary education classrooms. *Sustainability*, 12(10428), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su122410428>

Schuetz, R. L., Biancarosa, G., & Goode, J. (2018). Is technology the answer? Investigating students' engagement in math. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 50(4), 318–332.

Şengül, S., & Altinel, Ç. S. (2021). The examination of argumentation based problem solving processes of 10th grade students. *Acta Didactica Napocensia*, 14(1), 46–63. <https://doi.org/10.24193/adn.14.1.4>

Shenhav, A., Fahey, M. P., & Grahek, I., (2021). Decomposing the motivation to exert mental effort <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8528169/>

Smith, A., & Johnson, B. (2018). Impact of Classroom Design on Students' Perceptions of Learning Environment: A Case Study Approach. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 42(3), 345-358.

Staff, T.V. (2021). Pattern analysis is a critical 21st Century skill <https://www.teachervision.com/problem-solving/problem-solving-find-pattern>

Susilawati, W., Rachmawati, T. K., & Nuraida, I. (2021). Adaptive reasoning based on Microsoft Mathematics. *JTAM (Jurnal Teori Dan Aplikasi Matematika)*, 5(1), 216. <https://doi.org/10.31764/jtam.v5i1.3918>

Tremblay-Wragg, É., Raby, C., Ménard, L. and Plante, I. (2019). The use of diversified teaching strategies by four university teachers: what contribution to their students' learning motivation? *Teaching in Higher Education*, 1-18.

Troolin, A. (2023). How to Analyze an Argument's Effectiveness & Validity <https://study.com/academy/lesson/how-to-analyze-an-arguments-effectiveness-validity.html>

Urban, J., & Wilson, K. (2023). Drawing Conclusions | Definition & Examples <https://study.com/academy/lesson/drawing-conclusions-from-a-reading-selection.html>

Vandecandelaere M., Vanlar G., Spaybroeck S., De Fraine B., (2012) “The effect of students’ perceptions of the learning environment on the mathematics attitude” Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/259081100_The_effect_of_students'_perceptions_of_the_learning_environment_on_the_mathematics_attitude

Wan, T., Mickelsen, J., (2021). Investigating student ability to draw conclusions from measurement data <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2021perc.conf..432W/abstract>

Wang Y., Sperling R., (2020) “Characteristics of Effective Self-Regulated Learning “ Retrieved from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/feduc.2020.00058/full>

Wang, L., Peng, F., & Song, N. (2022). The impact of students’ mathematical attitudes on intentions, behavioral engagement, and mathematical performance in the China’s context. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1037853>

Wang, M. , Yang, Y. , He, Z. and Wang, M. (2022) The Proof of the $3X + 1$ Conjecture. *Advances in Pure Mathematics*, 12, 10-28. doi:

Weisstein, Eric W. (2019). Conjecture <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Conjecture>

Wulandari, S.Y., and Wutsqa, D.U., (2019). A study of junior high school students reasoning skill in mathematics <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/1320/1/012059>

Yanti, A. W., Sutini, & Kurohman, T. (2020). Adaptive reasoning profile of students in solving mathematical problems viewed from field-dependent and independent cognitive style. *AIP Conference Proceedings*. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0000699>

Zayyadi, M., and Kurniati, D., (2018). Mathematics reasoning and proving of students in generalizing the pattern https://www.researchgate.net/publication/32427323_Mathematics_reasoning_and_proving_of_students_in_generalizing_the_pattern

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